

Filipino Nurses Migration and the Future of Philippine Health Care

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Abstract

The migration of Filipino nurses outside the country affects the present and future of the Philippine health care system. The Delphi survey was an investigation on today's status of brain drain phenomenon among Filipino nurses and the future of Philippine health care from the viewpoints of some experts. A series of questionnaire was given to expert: (1) the first round asked about identifying issues revolving around brain drain; (2) the second was the anonymous feedback of all collected ideas and forecasts sent in the first round, which provided the experts with space to refine their own ideas; and (3) the last round summarized the inputs from the second questionnaire, and asked for additional clarification, strengths, weaknesses and new ideas. Filipino nurses migrate due to necessity. This is influenced by the physiologic, safety and security, social, self-esteem, and self-actualization needs of Filipino nurses, which is difficult to achieve in the local setting. Though there is oversupply of nurses in the country, skilled and intellectually competent nurses work outside. Common themes identified include: (1) poor remuneration; (2) poor working conditions; (3) unreasonable workloads; (4) lack of opportunities; and (5) insufficiently addressed basic needs.

Keyword: Delphi, Nurses Migration, Health Care

Introduction

The Philippines has been exporting nurses since the 1960's (CUTS Center for International Trade, Economics and Environment, 2010) and has provided the world with skilled care givers for decades. According to Currar and Immigration LLP (2010) it was then the intention of the government to educate Filipino nurses to work abroad making us up-to-date the largest nurse exporters. They further added that the country has been supplying 25 percent of all overseas nurses and among the nurses currently working 85 percent were estimated to be working internationally (Manila Times, 2003). Contrarily, Hutchcroft (1998a&b) pointed that, according to some health experts, if more and more nurses abandon the Philippines for higher salaries abroad the country's health care system will deteriorate. This was supported by, the former Philippine Nurses Association President, George Cordero's statement with the New York Times saying that the Filipino people will suffer because the U.S. will get all the trained nurses".

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1987). Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory was used as a point of departure in this study to establish what motivates the Filipino nurses to emigrate from Philippines. Hersey and Blanchard (1993) argued that this theory is concerned with an individual's needs and how satisfaction of needs, as well as deficits and unsatisfied needs, can change behavior. These authors argued that the behavior of individuals at a particular moment is usually determined by their strongest need. Just as when Filipino nurses attempt to seek greener pastures, they abandon their native land and try their lucks in foreign countries.

This Hierarchy of Needs Theory provides both a theory of human motives, by classifying basic human needs in a hierarchy, and a theory of human motivation relating these needs to general behavior (Wahba & Bridwell, 1976). Maslow argues (Moorhead & Griffin, 1995) that human beings have innate desires to satisfy a basic need at the bottom of the hierarchy. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs is depicted on five levels; the given set of needs, which are arranged in a hierarchy of importance, with the most three sets of needs at the lower levels are called deficiency needs because they must be satisfied for the

individual to be fundamentally comfortable, while the top two sets of needs are termed growth needs because they focus on personal growth and development.

According to Maslow (1987) the hierarchy into which human needs arrange them includes physiological, safety, belonging, esteem and self-actualization needs. Hersey, Blanchard and Johnson (2001) explain that once physiological needs become gratified the safety needs become predominant, and only when these needs are fairly well satisfied will social needs emerge as dominant. After individuals have satisfied these needs to some extent, they feel the need for esteem; both self-esteem and recognition from others, and once esteem needs begin to be adequately satisfied, the self-actualization needs become more dominant.

Human beings are motivated by unsatisfied needs, not by those that have been gratified (Moorhead & Griffin, 1995). Therefore nurses' unsatisfied needs could be seen as the push factors influencing the emigration of Filipino nurses. Gratification of needs in a foreign country could be seen as a pulling factor influencing the emigration of Filipino Nurses.

Figure 1. Hierarchy of Needs by Abraham Maslow (1943) and Laws of Migration by Ernest Ravenstein (1885; 1889).

The study is further anchored on the Laws of Migration by Ernest Ravenstein (1885, 1889). As known, people migrate for several and different reasons. These differences affect the overall migration process. The conditions under which a migrant enters a receiver population can have broad implications for all parties involved. Migration experience refers to the fact that different causes for migration will yield different results readily seen from a sociological perspective. That is why no theory can really best explain the migration process, though several attempts by theorists have been made to explain this but still to no avail no single theory best explains migration.

Theories of migration are important because they help us understand movements within wider political and economic contexts. For example, if outmigration from underdeveloped countries is shown to be a result of economic problems caused by the global economy, then such migration could be managed with better international economic agreements instead of restrictive immigration acts. A very good example of this is the Filipino nurse, because of economic reasons; nurses tend to try their luck in working abroad.

In the Laws of Migration developed by Ernest Ravenstein (1889) on migration, he concluded that migration was governed by a "push-pull" process; that is, unfavorable conditions in one place (poor living conditions, high crime rates, etc.) "push" people out, and favorable conditions in an external

location "pull" them out. He explained that the primary cause for migration was better external economic opportunities; the volume of migration decreases as distance increases; migration occurs in several stages; population movements are bilateral; and a person's demographics (e.g., gender, social class, age) influence a person's mobility.

Other theorists have patterned their theories on Ravenstein's theory. Everett Lee (1966) for instance, reformulated Ravenstein's theory to give more emphasis on the push factors. He outlined the impact of intervening obstacles on the migration process. He argued that variables like distance, physical and political barriers, and children or dependents can hamper the migration process. Migration is selective as it is dependent on age, gender, and social class as they affect how persons respond to push-pull factors, and these conditions also shape their ability to overcome the intervening obstacles. Personal factors also affect migration such as education, knowledge of a potential receiver population, family ties, which can either promote or stop migration.

Several theories were also developed to treat international patterns of migration on their own terms, but are also variants of push-pull theory. First, neoclassical economic theory (Sjaastad 1962; Todaro 1969) suggests that international migration is related to the global supply and demand for labor. Just as for Filipino nurses, nursing has been an in demand profession in other countries and the Philippines have been a main source of manpower for this demand. Nations, like the US, with scarce labor supply and high demand will have high wages that pull immigrants in from nations with a surplus of labor, like the Philippines.

Second, segmented labor-market theory (Piore 1979) argues that First World economies are structured so as to require a certain level of immigration. The US for instance, they allow immigration but up to a certain extent only. The theory suggests that developed economies have a primary market of secure, well-remunerated work and a secondary market of low-wage work. Segmented labor-market theory argues that immigrants are recruited to fill these jobs that are necessary for the overall economy to function but are avoided by the native-born population because of the poor working conditions associated with the secondary labor market. This may be true among as other countries view the nursing profession as a dirty job that their natives avoid it. Thirdly, world-systems theory (Sassen 1988) argues that international migration is a by-product of global capitalism. Contemporary patterns of international migration tend to be from the poor countries like the Philippines to the rich countries because factors associated with industrial development in the First World generated structural economic problems, and thus push factors, in the Third World.

Thus, it is the purpose of the study to make use of these laws of migration to further explain the migration process experienced by the Filipino nurses and how does this affect the current health care status of the country.

Statement of the Problem

The purpose of this study was to make an in-depth analysis on brain drain among Filipino nurses. This specifically answers the following questions: (1) How was the brain drain phenomenon experienced in the Philippines; and (2) What were the reasons why nurses work in other countries?

Method

The research utilized the Delphi survey method to gather relevant data from experts to provide understanding on the effects of massive migration of Filipino nurses. It provided a series of questionnaire to allow experts on specific knowledge to develop ideas about potential future development of brain drain phenomenon in the Philippines. The questionnaires were developed throughout the process in relation to the responses given by participants. Delphi surveys were used to gather collective forecasts about likely or possible developments in brain drain activity in regard to the Philippine health care. This was carried out face to face, online or by post. This was very useful since most expert participants were very busy people. The technique aimed to derive the benefit of the experts' opinions while avoiding the disadvantages of group thinking and group dynamics to avoid individual's domination (Polit & Beck, 2008).

The experts were nursing administrators from the academe and hospitals, social sciences and government sectors. They were subjected to three rounds of opinion poll. The first questionnaire asked the participants to individually identify issues revolving around the Brain Drain, generated ideas, and answered more closed ended questions such as the likely dates in predicting Philippine health care developments or deterioration. The second questionnaire anonymously was all the collected ideas and forecasts sent in the first round to all participants. This questionnaire also provided space for participants to refine each idea, commented on their strengths and weaknesses, and suggested new ideas about the topic. Additional questionnaire then summarized the input from the second questionnaire and asked for additional clarification, strengths, weaknesses, and new ideas. The third round summarized the forecasts which arrived in a consensus.

Results and Discussion

According to Stephen Bach (2001), the 2001-2004 Medium Term Philippines Development plan views overseas employment as a key source of economic growth. Filipino nurses are in great demand because they (Aiken, Buchan, Sochalski, Nichols & Powell, 2004): (1) are primarily educated in college-degree programs; and (2) communicate well in English.

In the view points of the experts, brain drain is a prevailing phenomenon viewed in a solitary context: a necessity. A nurse generally finds a better life outside the country. The amount of need varies contingent on a number of involving influences on nurses and their observed necessity of working outside the country. In fact, James Buchan and Julie Sochalski (2004) claimed that the Philippines is the largest source for nurses. During the 8th International Nursing Conference in Seoul Korea, held last October 27 to 28, 2011, it was identified that among countries in Asia, only the Philippines have nursing surplus. However, the surplus does not signify that brain drain did not occur. A large number of skillful and competent nurses migrate for a better living.

These were the current observations about the brain drain phenomenon among nurses: (1) young and brilliant nurses work or has the interest in working outside the country; (2) an increasing number of permanently employed nurses reaching a near retirable age - since the younger nurses leave the country to work; (3) there is an increasing demand for nurses with good to high pay outside the country inviting our competent nurses to work outside; (4) nurses receive less benefits and privileges here in the country especially in private institutions which is utterly dissimilar to the scenarios overseas; (5) an increasing and abundant number of newly registered nurses who do not consider working in the local setting for a long period of time, but instead considers the experience as staff nurse or volunteer nurse status as an opportunity to get a working experience for overseas registration or job application; (6) most nurses in the private institutions cannot sustain their daily basic needs; (7) abrupt resignation of a dominant number of young clinical instructors and staff nurses for work abroad compromising nursing academe and the health care setting; (8) there is a fast staff turnover of newly trained nurses that increases training expenses of hospitals and nursing schools; (9) poorly trained, less skillful, less competent, and less intelligent nurses comprised much of the bulk left.

A report from the Health Affairs (2004) claimed that the Philippines is motivated to produce nurses for export because of the remittance-income. Bruce Lindquist (1993) reported that Filipinos working abroad sent home more than \$800 million in remittance income.

Human beings are motivated by unsatisfied needs, not by those that have been gratified. Therefore nurses' unsatisfied needs could be seen as the push factors influencing the emigration of Filipino nurses (Ravenstein, 1889; Lee, 1966). Gratification of needs in a foreign country could be seen as pull factors influencing these nurses.

The following reasons were identified as to why nurses migrate: (1) nurses in the Philippines were paid in lower salary grade despite of the job complexities leading them to unmet financial obligations; (2) nurses invested a lot of money to finish nursing and yet they were not compensated well; (3) nurses need to sustain survival and get high paying job; (4) poor job, financial and health security for nurses in the country; (5) less opportunity for personal, cognitive, skill and career advancements; and (6) poor recognitions from the institutions they work.

Prystay (2002) and Lorenzo (2002) believed emigration of Filipino nurses could be threatening the country's health care quality. In the researchers own opinion, if the Philippine government can provide good work for the Filipinos in the Philippines, there is no need to export skillful workers. The countries strategy of culturing manpower is a proof of poor governance strategy. In order to improve a country, human resource is needed. It is just paradoxical that our country produce skillful workers for other countries benefit. If only the country can transform the workforce to be functional and productive - then maybe the Philippines will grow better economically.

"The outflow of skilled workers deprives developing countries of their human capital and results in brain drain with serious consequences on the delivery of key services like education or health care, and on economic productivity. In contrast, overseas work experience might provide opportunities to improve skills and further knowledge, while others whose qualifications are not recognised in their receiving country may see their skills diminish while abroad, making return difficult." (Dayton-Johnson, Pfeiffer, Schuettler & Schwinn, 2009).

Despite the migration of nurses to other countries where they can earn more, it was agreed and forecasted among experts that there will be no shortage of nurses in the country. In fact the country already had produced more than what is needed, and will continue producing more. "The country produces so many nurses but cannot absorb all of them locally," as supported by Philippine Overseas Employment Authority (POEA) regional director Francis Domingo on the issue on the exodus of nurses for overseas employment (Sunstar Newspaper, Feb. 2006).

The dean of a certain college of nursing dubbed her statistical knowledge that the country has 460 nursing schools, which produce 15,000 to 35,000, nurses annually. In spite of the oversupply of nurses in the country, there is a felt shortage of skilled, competent and specialized nurses. Trained, skilled and competent nurses continually migrate to work outside the country. The challenge is on how the country can convert beginners and the less skillful and competent to become nurse experts in different special areas. The cycle of training, retraining and enhancing the pool of potential unemployed, underemployed, less skillful and competent nurses will continue - since nurses will continually migrate not until reasonably high remuneration will be given.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers have come up with a conclusion that nursing brain drain exists in the Philippines characterized by great number of skillful and competent nurses going abroad. However, this does not signify shortage of Filipino nurses. The health care system will only be affected if the country could not transform the pool of inexperienced or less skillfull and competent nurses to become nurse experts.

References

- Aiken, L.H., Buchan, J., Sochalski, J., Nichols, B. & Powell, M. (2004). Trends in international nurse migration. Health Affairs. Project HOPE. Vol 23, no. 3: 69-77 doi: 10.1377/hlthaff.23.3.69.
- Bach, S. (2001). International migration of health workers: Labour and social issue. International Labour Office, Geneva
- Buchan, J. & Sochalski, J. (2004). Nurse Migration: Trends and the Policies. Trends and Practice. Bulletin of the World Health Organization.
- Curran and Immigration LLP (2010).Global Nurse Migration. Retrieved last October 18, 2010 from <http://curranberger.com/content/view/58/98/>
- CUTS Center for International Trade, Economics and Environment (2010).Barriers to Movement to Health Care Professionals.
- Dayton-Johnson, J., Pfeiffer, A., Schuettler, K. & Schwinn, J. (2009). Migration and Employment. Promoting Pro-Poor Growth: Employment. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.
- Dugger, C.W. (2006). U.S. Plan to Lure Nurses May Hurt Poor Nations. New York Times.Retrieved last October 18, 2010 from <https://www.nytimes.com/2006/05/24/world/americas/24nurses.html?pagewanted=print>
- Hersey, P. & Blanchard, K.H. (1993). Management of Organizational Behavior: Utilizing Human Resources, (6th ed). Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey.

- Hersey, P., Blanchard, K. H., & Johnson, D. E. (2001). *Management of organizational behavior: Leading human resources* (8th ed). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Hutchcroft, Paul D. (1998). "Neither Dynamo nor Domino: Reforms and Crises in the Philippine Political Economy," in T.J. Pempel editor, *The Politics of the Asian Economic Crisis*: Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Hutchcroft, Paul D. (1998). *Booty Capitalism: The Politics of Banking in the Philippines*: Ithaca: Cornell University Press.
- Lee, E. S. (1966). A Theory on Migration. *Demography*. Vol. 3 , No. 1 (1966), pp. 47-57.
- Lindquist, B. (1993). Migration Networks: A Case Study in the Philippines. *Asian and Pacific Migration Journal*. Vol 2, no. 1: 75-104.
- Lorenzo, F. (2002). *Nurse Supply and Demand in the Philippines*. Manila: Institute of Health Policy and Development Studies. University of the Philippines.
- Maslow, A. H. (1987). *Motivation and Personality* (1985 ed.). Cynthia McReynolds. New York: Harper and Row, Inc.
- Moorhed, G. & Griffin, R. W. (1995). *Organizational behavior: Managing people and organizations*. Houghton Mifflin, Boston.
- Piori, M. J. (1979). *Birds of Passage: Migrant Labor in Industrial Societies*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C. T. (2008). *Nursing research: Generating and assessing evidence for nursing practice*. (8 ed.). New York: J. B. Lippincott.
- Prystay, C. (202). U.S. Solution Is Philippine Dilemma: As Recruiters Snap Up More Nurses, Hospitals in Manila Are Scrambling. *Wall Street Journal*, 30 November 2002;
- Ravenstein, E. G. (1885). The Laws of Migration. *Journal of the Statistical Society of London*, Vol. 48, No. 2. (June, 1885), pp. 167-235.
- Ravenstein, E. G. (1889). The Laws of Migration. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society*, Vol. 52, No. 2. (June, 1889), pp. 241-305.
- Sassen, S. (1988). *The Mobility of Capital and Labor: A Study in International Investment and Labor Flow*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Sjaastad, L. (1962). The Cost and Returns of Human Migration. *The Journal of Political Economy*. 70(5):80-93.
- Sun Star (2006, February 15). Agency: No brain drain for nurses. *Sun Star*.
- Todaro, M. P. (1969). A Model of Labor Migration and Urban Unemployment in LDCs. *American Economic Review*, 59:138-148.
- Wahba, M.A. & Bridwell, L.G. (1976). Maslow reconsidered: A review of research on the need hierarchy theory. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance* , 15, 212-240.

References

Aiken, L.H., Buchan, J., Sochalski, J., Michols, B. & Powell, M. (2004). Trends in international nurse migration. *Health Affairs*. Project HOPE Vol 23, no. 3: 89-77 doi: 10.1377/hlthaff.23.3.89

Bach, S. (2001). International migration of health workers: Labor and social issues. *International Labour Office*. Geneva.

Buchan, J. & Sochalski, J. (2004). *Nurse Migration: Trends and the Policies*. Bulletin of the World Health Organization.

CUTS Center for International Trade, Economics and Environment (2010). *Barriers to Movement of Health Care Professionals*.

Dayton-Johnson, J., Pfeiffer, A., Schuetter, K. & Schwinn, J. (2009). *Migration and Employment: Promoting Growth and Economic Co-operation and Development*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

Dugger, C.W. (2006). U.S. Plan to lure Nurses May Hurt Poor Nations. *New York Times*. Retrieved October 18, 2010 from <http://www.nytimes.com/2006/05/24/world/americas/24nurses.html?pagewanted=print>

Hersey, P. & Blanchard, K.H. (1993). *Management of Organizational Behavior: Leading Human Resources*. (4th ed). Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey.